

Recipe for an Inclusion Revolution

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Culture refers to the customs, institutions, and achievements of a particular group of people. Science has a culture, as does the field of astronomy and astrophysics. In common with other cultures, astronomers have a language (equations and how we describe phenomena), traditions (how and when we do things, like clapping after talks and having 1–3 postdoc positions before a permanent job), and norms (expectations of how we are supposed to act, like asking questions in the middle of a talk). We have values (things we judge as significant to assessing scientific merit and things we deem less so), and we have our own art (how we give talks and take our data). At the virtual AAS meeting in June, my talk entitled “[The Inclusion Revolution](#)” was about acknowledging our culture and addressing the changes needed to make the field more diverse and inclusive, that is, how we must evolve the culture to achieve an inclusion revolution.

The Decadal Surveys are important to the culture of astronomy and astrophysics. As consensus documents, they affirm what is most important (values) and the norms of how we plan to accomplish our science over the subsequent 10 years, both inwardly to our community and outwardly as advice to the federal funding agencies. If we are interested in making cultural changes, then the Decadal Survey must play a part.

Although we might not think of the Decadal Survey as having the agency for cultural change now, these surveys certainly have played that role in the past. In the first Decadal Survey, in 1964, the community was concerned about the professional workforce and the lack of large public telescopes available to support graduate student observational research. From this primary concern, exclusivity of resources to do research, came the initiative to establish the national optical and radio telescope facilities. While now we may think of the Decadal Surveys as being about building satellites or telescope facilities, in fact, this first Decadal was all about enabling and expanding the opportunities for researchers to do their science by providing them with the necessary tools. The impact of the national facilities for astronomical research changed both the culture of astronomy and the workforce by shifting the ability to do observational research to institutions that did not have their own private telescopes. Now, as we look to make the field more diverse and inclusive, similar to what happened in 1964, we need to understand the barriers to participation in research and tackle them deliberately and strategically.

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underrepresented group in the field, and the [Women in Astronomy](#) conference series has long provided opportunities to address concerns about inclusion and how our traditions, norms, and values have not supported everyone in the field. However, the recognition of women's issues has not lifted all boats equally, in part because the concerns of other minority communities are different, and therefore the approaches to improvement must be different. Pipeline programs to support students are popular, but while fundamental to bringing more underrepresented minorities into the field, they do not address issues of retention.

In 2015, a grassroots group interested in promoting better inclusive practices, especially around intersectional identity, organized the [Inclusive Astronomy](#) meeting at Vanderbilt University. The goal was to provide recommendations for improving inclusivity by adjusting our norms, traditions, and values, particularly with respect to multiple intersections of identity. The sessions on “Access to Policy, Power, and Leadership” were envisioned to provide, especially to early-career researchers, information on centers of power in the field and how to put themselves in the rooms where they could bring about cultural change. This work carried into the [Inclusive Astronomy 2 \(IA2\)](#) conference where presentations were given on adjusting norms in collaborations through improved communication and codes of conduct. Other speakers cited efforts to identify metrics that enable an understanding of how changes in traditions, norms, and values are impacting the science we do and the ways we do it. They are using our language and our art to demonstrate the value of these changes for the science we accomplish.

These examples of informal institutional change have pushed conversations of comprehensive change forward. However, if we seek real cultural change in astronomy and astrophysics, we must also embrace formal institutional changes in departments, in projects, and at agencies. Formal change requires overhauling policies and procedures, and it must include strong incentives for people to make those changes through rewards and consequences. Listed below are three actions the community needs to embrace if we are to make meaningful changes.

Enable Broader Advisory and Resource Access

The make-up of science advisory and policy-making committees—and input to those committees—often come from a narrow group of scientists with experiences in science that are too similar. These narrow groups often don't even know what they don't know and underestimate barriers to inclusion that stymie good ideas. To better understand the needs of the whole community, we must diversify the experiences and expertise of advisory groups and the input given to committees and leaders who make decisions.

Understanding the barriers around access to resources is critical. We are losing opportunities for great science and for cultivating great scientists because of limited resources and access spread unequally. Survey data and large datasets have the potential to extend research opportunities to a broader community. But archival data alone, which often require additional resources to fully access and special expertise to navigate, are not enough. The development of science platforms and software tools can help provide services to support users and enable them to make the most of archival data. The [Astro Data Lab](#) and [ANTARES](#) projects at NOIRLab are intended to democratize the ability of individuals to do cutting-edge research by providing software tools that allow researchers to keep their scientific questions foremost in their minds as they navigate complex datasets and data products.

Tie Research Funding to Progress on Inclusion

Currently, funding for research is not tied to metrics or progress on inclusion of underrepresented and disenfranchised groups. “Broadening Participation” in our field must be about workforce and research participation, not just public outreach and education. If we are to make any progress on research inclusion, we must reward those who make inclusion part of their science goals and incentivize those who currently do not in order to adjust their thinking. For advancement, better practice around diversity and inclusion must be part of how we assess the scientific merit of our research. Until we embrace inclusion of a broader range of expertise and perspective in our research, we will not be doing the best science.

Bottom Up Is There; Top Down Is Lacking

As demonstrated in the examples above, individuals and groups have been making substantial progress on pushing for changes to our culture, i.e., what and whom we value in our pursuit of science, as well as the norms of what we expect of our scientific interactions and who can participate. However, at the highest levels of policy-making and funding support, discussions around inclusion in science are often shunned. We need leaders in high-level policy-making groups and at agencies to engage in the discussion for there to be traction, e.g., recommendations that insist on funding for inclusive programs, as well as access to resources for the broader community. In short, we need our leaders to lead on these issues.

As we look to the future, we need to get out of the more recently constructed box of thinking of the Decadal Survey as being just about the hardware and think about how we enable science by enabling access to resources for the broadest community to realize their scientific goals. This means embracing new traditions, norms, and values that will improve our culture and advance scientific discovery. We need the Decadal Survey to take a page out of its own history.

Further reading

[Norman, D. 2018, *AstroBeat*](#)

[Norman, D., et al. 2019, *BAAS*, 51\(7\)](#)

[Norman, D., et al. 2019, *BAAS* 51\(7\)](#)